

Bisphosphonate-Related Osteonecrosis of the Jaw Following Local Application of Alendronate Gel Around Dental Implants: A Case Report

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Abstract

Alendronate, which is a second-generation bisphosphonate (BP_s) are a class of drugs that are used to treat osteoporosis. It has been suggested that BP coating on dental implants have a positive effect on new bone formation. The purpose of this study was to assess the risk of bisphosphonate related osteonecrosis of the jaw (BRONJ) even when applied locally.

Materials and Methods: 12 systemically healthy patients with 30 edentulous sites aged between 24 years to 56 years desirous of replacing missing teeth with adequate width and height of edentulous area were included in the study. Patients were randomly divided into 2 groups experimental (implant coated with alendronate gel) and control group (implant coated without alendronate gel). Clinical and Radiographical parameters were evaluated at baseline (at the time of implant placement), 3months (at the time of prosthesis placement) and 6 months (3 months after prosthesis placement).

Results: Mean PPD showed significant changes at all time intervals and was slightly higher in the experimental group. MCB loss was radiologically lower for the experimental group, but was statistically non-significant when compared to control group. Difference in MBD around dental implants were statistically non-significant at all time intervals in both groups. Out of 30 edentulous sites 1 patients with two tests sites showed the sign of BRONJ.

Conclusion: No additional benefits of alendronate was found in our study, also two tests site showed signs of BRONJ despite the local application of alendronate gel.

Keywords: bisphosphonate, dental implants, osseointegration, Risk factors.

Introduction

Loss of tooth causes disharmony in dynamic occlusal equilibrium and also compromises with esthetic and masticatory or functional component of occlusion.¹ Implant surface is considered as one of the six important factors for successful Osseointegration. Implant surface can be modified by various method like physical modification, mechanical modification, biological modification, chemical modification and nano technology.² It has demonstrated that bio-modification of implant surface exhibited better implant-to-bone contact. A comprehensive codification system has been developed where surface characterization, made with standard analytical tools, describes the chemical composition and physical characteristics of the surface. Local factors influence the overall success and survival of implants which include primary stability at the time of implant placement,

the formation of a direct bone to implant contact (BIC), and the quantity and/or quality of the residual bone.³ Substantial efforts have been made to accelerate healing around implants.⁴ In this regard, adjunct therapies such as the placement of osteogenic coatings on implant surfaces have been proposed in an attempt to enhance BIC and new bone formation (NBF) around implant surfaces.⁵ Modifications in implant surface chemistry have also been reported to enhance the proliferation and differentiation of osteoprogenitor cells and to increase alkaline phosphatase (ALP) activity and the expression of osteogenic genes (which helps to enhance BIC and

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promote Osseointegration).⁶ Bisphosphonates (BPs) are carbon substituted pyrophosphate analogues that includes potent inhibitors of bone resorption. Alendronate (ALN) is an amino bisphosphonate which once taken up by bone acts as antiosteolytic agent. ALN binds to resorption surfaces and is locally released during the acidification with osteoclastic activity.⁷ This release leads to a rise in the local concentration of ALN, which results in an alteration in the ruffled border membrane characteristic of osteoclasts without destroying the cells. ALN demonstrates as a high potential inhibitor of alveolar bone resorption.⁸ Primarily ALN binds to the crystals of hydroxyapatite in bone and binds preferentially to bone resorption surface of those undergoing active osteoclastic resorption. It shows potent inhibitory effect on bone resorption by inhibition of osteoclasts and also has a direct effect on new bone formation. Both in-vivo and in-vitro use of ALN in human and animal research have shown decrease in the bone loss and increase in alveolar bone density. In dentistry, it was first used as a treatment of periodontal disease.⁹ Topical application of ALN was highly effective in reducing alveolar bone resorption after mucoperiosteal flap surgery. In recent years, ALN has been utilized in non-surgical periodontal therapy, periimplantitis management, root coverage procedures, management of furcation involvement and socket preservation.¹⁰ However, few clinical trials have been conducted pertaining to the effect of alendronate gel in surface treatment of dental implants.¹¹ ALN used as coating over dental implants has shown to inhibit the activity of osteoclast and accelerate the process of osseointegration which improves the connection between implant and bone.¹² Keeping in view the benefits of ALN gel, the present study was carried out to evaluate the efficacy of additional use of ALN gel on hard and soft tissue changes around dental implants.

Case Report

A patient reported for replacement of missing teeth in the posterior region of the jaw. The patient had no history of systemic illness, bisphosphonate therapy, radiation therapy, smoking, or any known risk factors associated with osteonecrosis of the jaw.

Clinical and radiographic examination revealed adequate bone height and width at the edentulous sites, making them suitable for implant placement. As part of a randomized clinical study, the patient was allocated to the experimental group, in which dental implants were coated with alendronate gel prior to placement (Figure 1). Two implants were placed under sterile conditions following standard surgical protocol (figure 2).

Postoperative healing during the initial follow-up period (Figure 3). The patient presented with pain, soft tissue inflammation, and delayed wound healing in the peri-implant region. Clinical examination revealed exposed bone surrounding both implant sites, associated with erythema and tenderness of the adjacent mucosa.

Despite initial conservative management, the exposed bone persisted. Radiographic assessment demonstrated

localized bone irregularity and early marginal bone loss around the affected implants (Figure 4). In the absence of systemic bisphosphonate use and other known risk factors, the clinical findings were suggestive of bisphosphonate-related osteonecrosis of the jaw associated with local alendronate application.

The patient was immediately placed on systemic antibiotic therapy, along with analgesics and antimicrobial mouth rinses. Despite conservative management, the implants failed to demonstrate signs of osseointegration, and the exposed bone persisted.

Owing to the failure of osseointegration and progression of necrotic changes, both implants were surgically removed (figure 5). Thorough debridement of the affected area was performed, and the mucoperiosteal flap was repositioned and a PRF membrane was placed and sutured for primary closure (figure 6 & figure 7).

Post-surgically, the patient underwent low-level laser therapy (LLLT) as an adjunctive treatment (figure 8). Laser therapy was initiated three days after implant removal and was administered at seven-day intervals for a total of three sessions (figure 9). Progressive improvement in soft tissue healing was observed, with resolution of pain and inflammation over subsequent follow-up visits (figure 10).

Discussion

Bisphosphonates have been extensively studied for their ability to inhibit osteoclastic activity and preserve peri-implant bone.¹³ Local delivery of bisphosphonates has been proposed as a means to enhance osseointegration while minimizing systemic exposure. However, the balance between beneficial suppression of bone resorption and excessive inhibition of bone remodeling remains critical.¹⁴

Al-Assaf and Bede evaluated the effect of locally applied alendronate on peri-implant tissues and reported improved bone density and reduced marginal bone loss around treated implants. Their findings suggested that controlled local delivery of alendronate may positively influence early bone healing by limiting osteoclastic resorption and enhancing peri-implant bone stability.¹⁵

Despite these reported benefits, the present case demonstrated early development of BRONJ-like signs within seven days of implant placement, followed by failure of osseointegration. This contrasts with the positive outcomes reported by Al-Assaf and Bede indicating that localized bisphosphonate application may not be universally safe. Excessive local concentrations of alendronate may suppress normal bone turnover, impair angiogenesis, and interfere with wound healing, thereby increasing susceptibility to osteonecrosis.^{15,16}

Similarly, Guimarães and Bueno¹⁷ investigated bisphosphonate modified implant surfaces and demonstrated local application of alendronate gel influenced the osseointegration negatively and had a visible effect on bone remodelling.^{17,18}

Most experimental and clinical studies evaluating bisphosphonate coated implants, have primarily focused on

osseointegration outcomes and marginal bone changes, with limited emphasis on potential adverse effects such as osteonecrosis.¹⁹ Furthermore, long-term safety data regarding localized bisphosphonate use in implant dentistry remain scarce.

In the present case, management consisted of systemic antibiotic therapy, removal of failed implants, primary flap closure, and adjunctive low-level laser therapy. Low-level laser therapy has been reported to enhance soft tissue healing, stimulate angiogenesis, and reduce inflammation, which may have contributed to clinical improvement following implant removal.²⁰

This case highlights that even in systemically healthy individuals, localized application of alendronate gel may pose a risk for impaired healing and early onset of BRONJ-like lesions. Therefore, careful case selection, cautious use of bisphosphonate-based implant surface modifications, and close postoperative monitoring are essential.

Conclusion

This case report demonstrates that localized application of alendronate gel may be associated with early development of BRONJ-like lesions and implant failure, even in systemically healthy individuals. Prompt diagnosis, implant removal, and adjunctive therapies such as low-level laser therapy are essential for effective management.

Figure: 1

Figure: 2

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